

An Investigation of the Challenges of Pakistani EFL Secondary School Teachers' During Covid 19

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Abstract:- This study aims to explore the results of online teaching in Gujranwala during covid 19. Furthermore, this study mainly focuses on EFL secondary school teachers' challenges regarding online teaching. Quantitative method has been used to conduct this study. Through the quantitative research tool, random sampling has done to fulfill the questionnaire of 30 EFL secondary school teachers of Gujranwala. The results of this study show that most of the teachers have no awareness regarding online teaching that's why teachers have faced more challenges to take the usage of online technology. This study is recommendation for future researchers that students, teachers, primary, secondary schools, colleges, and universities can play a significant role in the field of online teaching.

Keywords:- EFL Teachers, Online Teaching, Covide-19, Secondary School Level.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to social isolation, it is a technology that has been widely used by different educational systems in order to fulfill the academic needs of the students. It is considered the best and appropriate substitute when the world was suffering from unprecedented challenges. Although its implementation is full of challenges and initially a number of students all across the world are facing problems yet it is confirmed that its results are long-lasting. This remote and online learning has brought about a revolution in the field of digital education and in its absence, it might take years to do so (Lurvnik 2020).

The present shift from traditional ways to this online learning has also opened ways for teachers as well as for students to become more strong, creative, and innovative (Yokozeki 2020). The social isolation and rapid increase of the coronavirus have also caused fear, anxiety, and many other concerns among citizens around the world (NCIRD 2020). However, there are concerns among those who are involved in educational fields who are facing challenges while conducting online learning due to the lack of knowledge in this field. In addition to this, it has been reported that a tremendous shift to online teaching has caused stress and anxiety among teachers in different parts of the world (ibid. 2020). Furthermore, it has been observed that there are many hurdles that may prove detrimental to learning online.

It has also been assumed that in Pakistan, there is a mixed view among the students and teachers regarding learning online teaching. Besides, it was also confirmed that what are the factors that may prove as an opportunity among teachers and students. Contrary to this, there are some challenges in terms of good internet connection, motivation level by teachers and students, role of parents, a connection between students and teachers, and it can require some amount of time to overcome these challenges. Since this shift is totally new and there is a huge gap observed by different scholars that need to be solved and a lot of work can be done in this field. Currently, there are few pieces of works that have been conducted on this subject. **Statement of the problem:** Teachers' response regarding online teaching challenges during covid 19 situations and online teaching effects on teachers as well as learners. This research mainly focuses on EFL secondary school teachers of Gujranwala during online teaching.

➤ *Delimitation*

Teachers participated to validate the results of this study through online questionnaire answers by 30 teachers of private secondary school level of Gujranwala.

➤ *Research Objective*

This study aims to find the strategies to overcome the problems of EFL secondary school teachers as well as important factors that can affect the EFL school teachers' online teaching during covid 19.

➤ *Research Questions*

1-What are the strategies to overcome the problems of EFL school teachers? 2-What are the important factors that affect the EFL school teachers' online teaching during covid 19?

➤ *Significance of the Study*

This study has revealed what are the strategies to overcome the problems of EFL school teachers and the important factors which affect the EFL school teachers' teaching during covid 19.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section evaluates 6 empirical studies selected from 15 articles about online teaching during COVID-19. These studies have been done in the context of Iran, Nepal, Israel, and Canada to reflect the current issues and developments in the area of online teaching. It aims to describe the current uncertain and pandemic situation as a result of COVID-19. It also analyzes and compares the research methods and findings of other studies done in the same area. It has been observed in recent days that the spread of COVID-19 has caused widespread fear, anxiety, and fear among the citizens living all around the world (NCIRD 2020). This part is an attempt to notice the secondary school teachers' challenges associated with the integration of technology in past studies. It has been noted that the English language curriculum is incorporating technologically advanced tools and ways in order to improve the learning and teaching context with a desire to solve the existing challenges faced by the teachers in this field. For example, recent years have witnessed that a number of language classrooms have adopted the dominant technologies ranging from online presentation to the online application (Adan et al., 2019).

Apart from that, it is checked that either teacher has direct access to the internet, alone room, ability to learn technology and their level of knowledge or not, and what are the factors that are going to contribute to make them professionals in this field. It proved to be a problem in those countries where technology was not developed and advanced prior to this pandemic (UNESCO, March 2020). This portion also gives us an overview of the opinions and beliefs of the other researchers, identifies the prominent issues faced by the secondary school teachers during a teaching in this scenario conditioned by COVID-19. These days, language learning and teaching are widely considered interesting subjects across the world. It has been observed that the English language and learning have gone through many hard phases over the past few years. The main role of EFL teachers is to introduce a kind of powerful curriculum that may be very useful, innovative, and productive in terms of overcoming all of those obstacles (Jiang, May, @ Qin, 2018). However, in some areas of the country or in general, all around the world there are some limitations in terms of using technologies and that is the dominant reason that teachers are preferring to take traditional classrooms rather than focusing on implementing technologies in the classrooms.

Besides, there are some issues regarding the satisfaction of the teachers who are reluctant to go for online classes as it may prove a very daunting task to design the material for the online class. Apart from that, it requires tremendous effort to conduct online class as it may be very time consuming and hard for those teachers who are habitual of teaching with traditional patterns (Mahmoudzadeh, 2014). In order to better understand the teacher's perspective about online teaching, this study deeply examines all researches taking place in the field of online teaching and highlights the key issues such as isolation, personal factors, and lack of practical experience. Present circumstances caused by the social isolation and other personal factors have left deep influences among parents who

do not seem to be prepared to assist their children for online learning because of the lack of access to the essential technology and fast internet or the lack of ability to use the technology to meet with this unprecedented challenge. (UNESCO 2020). It is widely accepted that the key component of initial teacher education programs is the practical experience in educational institutions. (Allen and Wright 2014) is of the view that one of the main obstacles facing the teacher during the COVID-19 lockdown was the practical experience in educational institutions or lack thereof.

This portion emphasizes that all the teaching methodologies are adopted to fulfill the student's needs and it is the responsibility of the teachers that they must design methodology that best fulfills the needs of every individual. A number of studies that have previously been conducted to find the factors that are influential in producing positive results in conducting technology-oriented classes suggest that there is a need to know the interaction that exists between teachers, students, and technology (Honey et al. 2000). Despite the fact that there is positive feedback coupled with a huge number of benefits reported by various studies, there are few challenges that are needed to be highlighted in order to overcome them. There is a tendency among some people that traditional classes may be more important than online ones (Che Mus, Koo, & Azmam, 2012).

To understand the impacts of school closures and the newly adopted ways that are going to be entirely different, there is a need to understand the difference between a 'normal' education and the education that is going to be organized behind a socially distant environment. It is evident that normal education was community divorced because it takes children away from home and community and the latter is community embedded because it is conducted within the homes and residences of the students (Mahboob 2020). Mahboob further argues that there are multiple factors and variations and due to the parents have different sorts of access to information based on their social, economic, linguistic, and educational background. In order to mobilize home and community, the backgrounds and the limitations of the home and community need to be an important consideration. In other words, it must be understood that education during COVID-19 and beyond must be imagined as a community-embedded practice. It is to be noted that teachers in community-embedded education provide resources and help the students in getting reliable resources. There is a need to understand that the actual realization of the educational practice seems to depend on the facilities, resources, skills, and expertise of those involved in the process (Mehboob 2020). Since these studies are primarily focused on inculcating the latest technologies in EFL classrooms and recognizes the challenges of secondary school teachers, therefore such devices are highly considered not conducive in hard situations such as the COVID-19 pandemic which has caused a disturbance in all aspects of life including education and learning for all countries and the example of Pakistan is not exceptional. This gap in the literature and all other concerned fields have urged us to conduct a study that aims at understanding the challenges faced by EFL teachers by using technology during this pandemic in Gujranwala.

III. METHODOLOGY

➤ *Research Paradigm*

This research is in descriptive design, through a quantitative research approach data has been collected and random sampling has followed to fill the questionnaire.

➤ *Population*

EFL secondary school teachers of Gujranwala who are teaching at secondary school are the population of this research.

➤ *Sample*

30 EFL secondary school teachers of Gujranwala have been selected as the sample of this research.

➤ *Data Collection*

Through an online survey link data has been collected from EFL secondary school teachers. All school teachers have filled this questionnaire through WhatsApp.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1 Descriptives Data Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Identify yourself, you are:	30	2	2	2.00	.000
During the Coronavirus pandemic, was the online learning experience successful in Gujranwala?	30	1	2	1.23	.430
Some may consider this experiment to be a success. What are the reasons that led them to this belief? (More than one answer can be selected here)	30	1	4	2.40	1.133
Some may consider this experiment to be a failure. What are the reasons that led them to this belief? (More than one answer can be selected here)	30	1	4	1.80	.997
Valid N (listwise)	30				

Table 2 Statistics

Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics
Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics
Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics

Table 3 Frequency Table

Identify yourself, you are:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid A teacher	30	93.8	100.0	100.0
Missing System	2	6.3		
Total	32	100.0		

This part of the study was primarily focused on the participant’s identity and most of the participants who were made the part of this research were teachers. Since teacher’s role is widely considered pivotal in online learning and that was the reason it was ensured that maximum number of teachers participate in this research.

Table 4 During the Coronavirus pandemic, was the online learning experience successful in Gujranwala?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	23	71.9	76.7	76.7
	No	7	21.9	23.3	100.0
	Total	30	93.8	100.0	
Missing	System	2	6.3		
	Total	32	100.0		

This was a kind of survey study to get an idea that how successful online learning proved during COVID-19. This question was asked from 30 teachers who are currently teaching at different institutes. It was found that 71.9 percent of participants were of the view that it was a successful experience and only 21.9 percent of participants considered it a failure which incurs that overall, it seems to be a successful idea according to the selected participants.

Table 5 Some may consider this experiment to be a success. What are the reasons that led them to this belief? (More than one answer can be selected here)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Students' commitment to participate	11	34.4	36.7	36.7
	The good communication between the teacher and his students	15	46.9	50.0	86.7
	Teacher's ability to teach online	4	12.5	13.3	100.0
	Total	30	93.8	100.0	
Missing	System	2	6.3		
	Total	32	100.0		

This section is concerned with the participants who are in favor of online teaching and consider it a success despite the unprecedented challenges faced by the people during COVID-19. In the first question, it was asked that how much students were committed to learning online that made this technology-based teaching successful. It was found that 34.4 percent of participants considered commitment key thing that is pivotal to make it a successful idea. In the second question, 46.9 percent of participants made it clear that good communication between teachers and students is the reason that can make this research very productive in terms of getting successful. In the last question which was related to the ability of teachers' ability to teach online and it was surprising to know that only 12.5 percent of teachers considered it a reason for this.

Table 6 Some may consider this experiment to be a failure. What are the reasons that led them to this belief? (More than one answer can be selected here)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Students' lack of participation	14	43.8	46.7	46.7
	Teacher's lack of experience in teaching online	12	37.5	40.0	86.7
	A slow internet connection	4	12.5	13.3	100.0
Missing	Total	30	93.8	100.0	
	System	2	6.3		
	Total	32	100.0		

In this figure, a question was asked to get an idea that what are the factors that are considered responsible for the failure of online education. Besides, it also indicates that which reasons led these participants toward this belief. It was surprised that most of the students considered the first factor responsible behind the failure of online education which describes that students lack participation is the reason that most of the students are not in favor of online education. This research was conducted in Gujranwala and contrary to

technologically advanced countries; it was found that teachers are not very much familiar with technology and this may be the reason that 37.5 percent of participants considered it the second most responsible factor that made them think that learning online is a flawed idea. In addition to this, there is a surprising result in the last question which was related to the internet speed and it was found that only 12.5 percent considered it a reasonable factor behind the failure of online teaching.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

❖ Findings:

- While conducting this research, it has been observed that the greatest number of participants found online learning very innovative despite of all the challenges.
- Before conducting this study, it was assumed that some participants may complain about the internet connectivity.
- But contrary to this, less than 15 percent of participants considered it a hurdle on the way of online learning.
- In addition to this, more than 70 percent of participants showed their interest in online learning thus making it a fully reliable way of learning, and less than 25 percent of participants considered it a failure during COVID-19.
- It has also been observed that more than 50 percent of participants ascertain that proper communication bounding between teachers and students is the best possible way to make it a fully successful experience during this pandemic.
- On the other hand, more than 45 percent of participants who considered it a failure were of the view that students' lack of participation is the primary reason behind its failure.
- Whereas, 38 percent participants considered that teachers lack of experience in online learning is the reason behind its failure.

❖ Recommendations

- This study was conducted in Gujranwala and teachers at the secondary level were made part of this research. COVID-19 is an entirely new phenomenon that has caused social isolation in many parts of the world.
- There is still a huge gap that is needed to be fulfilled and it's a great opportunity for others to conduct same research at university, primary school, or college levels.
- This study addressed the challenges faced by the students, and teachers during COVID-19 and it seem to be very productive in that it has successfully addressed all of these issues ranging from internet connectivity, students' and teachers' bounding to students' participant and teachers' ability to teach online.
- A researcher may conduct research in specifics variables which include the teachers experience regarding online teachings or students experience and their objections.
- In a nutshell, this study is highly recommended to interested researchers for further research and all the areas have been highlighted that are still needed to be addressed.
- Online facilities can play important role in strengthening institutions but unfortunately, our most of institutions have not proper information regarding online teaching. Therefor it is recommended for future researchers to complete this gap.
- Teachers' lack of awareness regarding online teaching is also a major gap which future researchers can fulfill in a perfect way.

- Students should also be involved in e-learning technology usage this gap can be fulfilled by future researchers.

❖ Conclusion

This study explores the challenges of EFL secondary school teachers during covid 19. Teachers' lack of awareness regarding online technology is the major problem of this study. This study has also revealed the failure results of online teaching in covid 19 situations and affects their teaching and students' learning. Additionally, there are some significant reasons regarding teaching like internet connectivity, teachers' knowledge about technology usage are the main issues that affect teaching. But on the other hand, 70 percent of the participants are agreed to accept that online learning is a fully reliable source. Overall, this study seems to produce wonderful results and all the questions asked in the earlier sections have been successfully answered. Besides the positivity of this study has also opened new ways for further study and a researcher may find this study useful in terms of satisfying our needs.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Jiang, L., Zhang, L. J., & May, S. (2016). Implementing English-medium instruction (EMI) in China: Teachers' practices and perceptions, and students' learning motivation and needs. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*. doi:10.1080/13670050.2016.1231166)
- [2]. Mahmoudzadeh, S. (2014). The Effect of Using PowerPoint on Iranian EFL Learners' Knowledge of Abstract Vocabulary. *International Conference on Current Trends in ELT*
- [3]. Mahboob, A. (2020). Education in the time of COVID-19. Available at: <http://flcgroup.net/courses/education101-intro/>
- [4]. Che Musa, N., Koo, Y., & Azman, H. (2012, January). Exploring English Language Learning and Teaching in Malaysia. *GEMA Online™ Journal of Language Studies*, 12(1), 35-51.
- [5]. Adnan, A., Ahmad, M., Yusof, A., Mohd Kamal, M., & Mustafa Kamal, N. (2019). English Language Simulations Augmented with 360-degrees spherical videos (ELSA 360°-Videos): 'Virtual Reality' Real Life Learning! *International Invention, Innovative & Creative Conference (InIIC Series 1/2019)*.
- [6]. NCIRD, (2020). Coronavirus Disease 2019. National Center for Immunization and Respiratory Diseases (NCIRD). Division of Viral Diseases. Marre nga: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/daily-life-coping/managing-stress-anxiety.html> Palmer, I., Dunford, R., & Akin, G. (2009). Ed 2. *Managing Organizational Change-A Multiple Perspective Approach*
- [7]. UNESCO (2020). Covid-19 Impact on Education Data. COVID-19 Education Disruption and Response. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO. Paris, France